

Review

Supply Chain Risk Assessment in Automotive Industry of Pakistan: A Review

Maria Sadiq^{1*}, Hanan Afzal²

¹Alfalah Institute of Business & Finance (IBF), Bahauddin Zikriya University (BZU), Multan, Pakistan (Email: mariasadiq66@gmail.com)

²National University of Modern Languages, Multan Campus, Multan, Pakistan (Email: hafzal@numl.edu.pk)

*Corresponding author

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Abstract: Risk is intrinsic to all aspects of life and has repercussions, but it is susceptible when it occurs, specifically in supply chains. The purpose of this paper is to review past literature on the management of supply chain risk reported in General Management, Supply Chain Management, and Risk Management research. We construct a description of what we find to be the crucial supply chain challenges of the automotive sector, based on previous analysis, and use it to format the analysis. Furthermore, seventeen risks were identified. Results suggest that Product production delays, manufacturer consistency issues, vendor contact faults, and forecasting mistakes are the most exposed threats in the automobile's supply chains in Pakistan.

Keywords: supply chain risk management; supply chain risk; supply chain management

Introduction

The supply chain consists of a complex structure of sharing information, material, goods, finance, and other resources from an internal department to an outside company And then on to the final client. However, supply chains are prone to risk factors like globalization, multiple product variants, dependency on suppliers, outsourcing, and environmental damage prevailing internal and external to the supply chain, which causes supply chain disruptions (Shahbazi et al., 2013). Supply chain disruption has a critical effect on a company's financial, operational, short term, and long-term performance. The more complex business activities are more open to supply chain risks. To maintain supply chain performance, companies must quickly respond to the risk of whether they are internal or external. It requires that supply chains must be deeply understood,

and supply chain managers must know how to manage risks in their supply chains. When it particularly comes to the automotive industry, which considered one of the advanced industries and consists of multiple small and complex steps in the manufacturing process. It has numerous tier suppliers, which sometimes threaten the flow of material. Due to this, there is an increase in supply chain risks in the auto sector; on the other hand, a decrease in financial and operational performance has occurred in recent years. According to the report published by McKinsey, 71% of automotive companies in America were facing supply chain disruptions in America in 2010. The statistics show that supply chains in the automotive industry face risks like never before, and automotive companies are indulging in identifying, assessing, measuring, and managing risk in their supply chains. In managing SCR, the more complicated step is risk identification, a process of discovering and defining the risk. There are different methods of identifying risk, and organizations use their methods to identify the risks. Once the company recognizes the risks, then they categorize them according to their nature. The second most crucial step is risk measurement or risk assessment, in which different risks are measured, assessed according to their probability of occurrence, and prioritizes according to their severity (Aqlan, 2015).

Our underlying supposition is that car companies have specific risk management strategies requirements. We have examined the existing literature in supply chain management, general management, and risk management literature to support our conclusions and carry out a comprehensive analysis of the current research on SCRM in automobile companies. Over the next segment, we offer reasons why we assume that there are specific guidelines for the management of supply chain hazards in the auto market. We then present the overall results of our research quest for SCRM in automotive industries, as presented in journal articles. Next, we add a basic table listing all potential threats to the supply chain, taken from previous studies. Finally, we finish with the future work plan

Research Background and Significance

i. Supply Chain Risk

Due to turbulent changing environments like innovation, improvement in technology, outsourcing, globalization, and unforeseen events, the risk is inherent in almost all aspects of life. Uncertainty is the reason behind the occurrence of risk because we don't know what will happen in the future. Mitchell (1995) defined risk as "the likelihood of loss and the significance of that

loss to the organization or individual." Risk can be forecasted but can't be measured totally, and there is uncertainty about what will happen in the future and leaves a gap between what we have already planned and what happens (Waters 2007). Whatever the situation is, risk has the severe potential of harm and loss to the organizations, and they must assess it. Risk management involves two crucial steps, risk identification, and risk assessment, which consists of understanding those conditions which create problems and then evaluate their likelihood of occurrence and negative impact (Tapiero 2007). Since the mid-twentieth century, organizations have broadened their risk management approach to issues like insurance, safety, public relations, and finance to supply chains. And this is because of severe disruptions in the supply chains regularly (Norman and Lindroth 2004). Supply chain disturbances are unscheduled incidents that interrupt the regular movement of goods in the supply chains. It not only halts the operations, but it takes a long recovery time if not prepared already (Hendrick and Singhal 2005). Juttner (2003) defined supply chain risk as "a variation in the distribution of possible supply chain outcomes, their likelihood, and their subjective values."

Different researchers have presented the definition of supply chain risk according to its nature, impact, and severity. Although researches have proposed definitions of supply chain risk due to the divergence, different terminologies, approaches, and practices, their applicability is only to a specific context, which depends on the location of the study nature of the study and meaning of the study. However, the definition of supply chain risk presented by Zsidisin (2004) is considered comprehensive; he defined Supply chain risk as "probability of an incident associated with inbound supply from an individual supplier failure or the supply market occurring, in which its outcomes result in the inability of, the purchasing firm to meet the customers demand or causes threats to the customer's life and safety."

In Juttner (2003) and Zsidisin (2004), one thing in common they have focused on the fundamental aspects of the risk, which are related to possible outcomes, probability of occurrence, and subjective values. On the other hand, recently, authors focused more on the flow of variability and said risk as variability in the distribution of material and information flow in various interfaces of the supply chain. This change in risk perception of risk highlighted the need for analyzing and assessment of risks. Lavastre et al. 2012 defined supply chain risk as: "Those small events and incidents that happen to one or several parts in the supply chain and affect the whole supply chain negatively and restricts in achieving organizational goals."

ii. Supply Chain Risk in the Automotive Industry

In this research, we have specifically focused on supply chain risk in the automotive sector. The reason behind choosing the auto industry is that past decades have changed the ways of doing business, and automobile industry supply chains are facing more severe risks than they have ever encountered. Supply chain risk in the car sector is not defined by any researchers yet, and they have used the definitions of supply chain risk defined by previous researchers like (Juttner 2003, Zsidisin 2004, Christopher and Peck 2004, and Lavastre et al. 2012). Instead, they have focused more on the reasons/factors of risks arising in the automobile sector's supply chains, which we have concluded in this section, and also tried defining Supply chain risk in the car sector. According to Thun and Hoenig (2011a), significant reasons for risk arising in the vehicle supply chain are complexity, efficiency, and uncertainty. Multiple product variants and supplier dependencies create problems because if the supplier defaults, the flow of material stops (Wagner and Bode, 2009). Automotive firm supply chains consist of different kinds of risks with low probability and high impact. High impact and low probability risk factors are hard to predict because of the uncertainty, and they are even difficult to manage when they occur. That is why managers leave some of these risks and don't take the necessary measures and leave the firm exposed to these kinds of threats (Levi et al. 2015). From the above discussion, we have summed up and coming with a new definition of supply chain risk, specifically in the vehicle sector, which will guide researchers and practitioners in solving the real-life problems associated with supply chain risk in the automobile sector. Our proposed definition of supply chain risk in the car sector is:

"All those events that happen within or outside the supply chain whether they are related to micro and macroeconomic, industry, organizational, environmental, operational and stream (upstream and downstream) affects the whole supply chain negatively, and disruptions caused by them creates hurdles in achieving goals of the automotive company."

iii. Supply Chain Risk in Automobile Sector in Pakistan

The auto sector in Pakistan consists of small numbers of the manufacturer, vendors, and OEMs, but it still contributes to the economy in terms of revenue, foreign exchange, and employment. The automotive industry of Pakistan's annual turnover is calculated as PKR 30 billion. The sector consists of several producing units for original components and more than

2000 vendors with an investment of USD 1.09 billion. Regarding these statistics, as per the author's information, no previous work is available that deals with SCR of the vehicle companies in Pakistan. And it would be the first attempt to explore this area and fulfill the research gap in the literature. Therefore, we have mainly focused on this research on the assessment of the risk of a supply chain in the car companies of Pakistan. First of all, we defined the SCR in the industry of vehicles. Now, we have proposed a definition of supply chain risk in the vehicle industry of Pakistan.

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Related Theories and Review of Literature

Related Theories

Supply chain risk literature is rich in research, but when it comes to the implementation of supply chain theories or extracting results from approaches than the studies are scarce. According to the comparison made by Fan and Stevenson (2017) from 2000 to 2016, 45 studies on SCR literature have used its theories in their research. Some of the most related opinions to supply chain risk literature are as follows:

i. Resource Dependence Theory

This theory suggests that firms engage with other firms and partners to gain resources for their well-being. This theory depends on the principle of resource dependence concerning the idea of the SC. Members of the chain are dependent on each other, and disruption in one part causes disorders in other elements (Pfeffer and Salancik, 1978). The basis of the argument is that firms are affected by the external environments, and to perform well, they need to manage their resources by setting multiple inter-firm arrangements. In the article "Synthesizing and Extending Resource Dependence Theory: A Meta-Analysis," which was published in 2013 by Drees and Heugens (2013), 157 tests were conducted, and results summarize that theory is the basis for understanding the firms-environmental relationships.

ii. Relationship Exchange Theory

It is one of the most popular theories in economics, explaining the relationships between different business partners. This theory suggests a balance between company rewards and costs. In the supply chain sense, this theory is considered as a relationship-building theory due to the exchange of relationships between different firms. If a firm has good relations with its suppliers, vendors, and other partners, it is rewarded with higher profits otherwise with higher costs. So, maintaining relationships creates a balance between rewards and costs (Fan and Stevenson, 2017).

iii. Contingency Theory

According to the contingency theory situation never remains the same, and there is always a risk of ever-changing conditions, so an organization can't be lead with defined patterns. A vigilante leader in the organization and a highly qualified team can judge the situation and act accordingly (Fan and Stevenson 2017). Moreover, the theory suggests that external circumstances are more active in firm performance, so managers or responsible persons should act accordingly to the situations. The theory tells about external risk prevailing in supply chains and suggests being proactive in handling the job on time.

iv. Manufacturing Strategy Theory

Manufacturing theory suggests that different firms have different manufacturing designs. Furthermore, the approach will be a manufacturing mechanism with a tailored configuration that represents the goals and trade-offs found in the company's business position and strategy. (Bradley, 2004). Two new concepts were involved in light of this theory, Lean production and Just in time. Both are valuable concepts in supply chain literature (Cheng, 1996).

ii. Information processing theory

Information processing theory suggests timely information sharing between a firm supply chain from one partner to the other. If the information regarding risk or damage is reported in time to all partners in the supply chain, it prevents it from disrupting the supply chain. How data is processed, and firms react to the information are an essential point to measure in supply chain risk literature.

iii. Normal accident theory

According to Normal Accident Theory, as the firm moves toward more complex systems, accidents become a part of the routine (St. Pierre, et al., 2008). The theory suggests that complex systems are made up of small and large multiple steps, and a problem in one can cause problems in all. So it should be prioritized to make the systems more accessible.

Literature Review

Supply chain management is a concept which evolved in the mid-1980s and is in practice by the organizations. Implementing the idea of supply chain management has improved organizations' performance, but it is still facing new issues and challenges. Due to the changing business environment, circumstances, and issues like globalization, outsourcing, demand volatility, market saturation, multiple suppliers, terrorist attacks, and environmental changes, the risk is evolved in supply chains and have forced manufacturing firms to establish the concepts of risk assessment in their supply chains. Due to this, the term "risk" has gained much attention in the supply chain concept, and researchers have widely used it. So, a new idea took place in supply chain management known as supply chain risk. Organizations are now considering risks in their supply chains, and they are trying to mitigate these risks to reduce supply chain disruptions. In general, it does not clear among supply chain managers worldwide what the numerous risks are causing disruptions in their supply chains. There is a difference of opinion among different parts of the world in supply chain managers and logistics managers.

Therefore, researchers have focused on different risk factors and tried to assess their impact on supply chains. Sodhi et al., (2012) have written twelve articles on supply chain risk and tried to cover it in the literature of supply chain risk management, but the view is quite diverse and different. Christopher and Peck (2004) identified five main categories of supply chain risk: production risk, controlling risk, market risk, supply risk, and environmental risk. On the other hand, Chopra and Sodhi (2004) identified nine major categories of threats in the supply chains: interruption risk, delay risk, network risk, prediction risk, asset risk, acquisition risk, inventory risk, receivables risk, and capability risk. According to Jüttner (2005), supply chain risks are evolved from five sources: environment, control, processes, demand, and supply. Operations are divided into two types of internal firm processes and inter-organizational processes. Internal

firm processes are linked to the planning of a product, product production, and delivery. Alternatively, inter-organizational processes are linked to supply forecasting and supply partners.

Kleindorfer and Saad (2005) specifically focused on the disruption risks and come up with three sources of disruption risks: the first one is an operational contingency, which includes the malfunction of equipment and failure of systems. The second source is natural hazards related to earthquakes, hurricanes, storms, and bad weather. The third source represents the political instability in the country and terrorism. Kiser and Cantrell (2006) distributed risk into two categories internal threats and external risk. Internal risks are associated with manufacturing risk, business risk, planning, and mitigation and control risk. In contrast, other risks are external and are defined as supply and demand risk, environment risk, business risk, and physical risk). In another study, Supply Chain Risk is categorized into five groups: demand-side risk, supply-side risk, regulatory risk, legal and procedural risk, and infrastructure risk (Wagner and Bode, 2008).

According to Tang and Tomlin (2008), supply chain risks can be divided into six types: supply risk, demand risk, process risk, behavioral risk, intellectual property risk, and socio-political risk. But in their study, they have focused only on supply, demand, and process risks and have ignored the other three risks.

Moreover, it not only depends on what are the risk factors and how they influence supply chains, but it also depends on firm characteristics like the business sector, flexibility in the business and operations, level of maturity, organizational structure, and its processes. It can be said that these characteristics influence not only firm performance but also supply chain risks and management. Trkman and McCormack (2009) suggested a model for supply chain risk, which consists of four influencers. (i) Supplier attributes, (ii) supply chain strategy, (iii) endogenous uncertainty, and (iv) Exogenous change. Supplier attributes are related to operational factors, financial performance, human resources, relationships, and cultural factors. Supply chain strategy is related to the type of supply chain that is lean or agile or hybrid, a variety of suppliers, the structure of the business, and the geographic location of a business. Endogenous uncertainty is divided into two parts market instability and technical turmoil. Market turbulence is related to new customers, new products, price sensitivity, competition level, and demand fluctuations. Technology turbulence is similar to high-tech information and rapid change in technology. Finally, exogenous uncertainty is related to outside environments like labor strikes, terrorism, natural disasters, inflation, interest rate, GDP, and commodity prices.

Risk can't be managed until it is identified accurately; risk identification is an art that identifies the specific dangers prevailing in the organization and allows managers to respond to them in appropriate manners. The process of supply chain risk management includes risk identification, risk assessment, risk mitigation, and risk monitoring (Blackhurst and Wu, 2009). Due to the reasons discussed above, managing supply chain risk is a point of interest for supply chain managers, and they pay a lot of attention to it due to its negative on their business. Before managing risk, its assessment is necessary, prioritizing each risk with its probability of occurrence and impact. There are different kinds of risk assessment techniques like quantitative, qualitative, and hybrid. A wide range of previous researchers has used these techniques to depict the best results for their studies. Failure mode and effect analysis (FMEA), empirical analysis, and process performance modeling are the examples of qualitative techniques used by (Sinha et al., 2004; Thun and Hoenig, 2011; Wanger and Bode, 2006; and Tazelaar and Snijders, 2013).

As far as quantitative techniques are concerned, they are analytical optimization and simulation techniques. Sarkar and Mohapatra, 2009; Sawik, 2011; Goh et al., 2007 used systematic optimization techniques in their studies. Kumar and Tiwari (2013) used an analytical risk modeling technique in his research. Simulation is a technique used to visualize risks in the supply chain and is better used in supply chains with stochastic nature. The simulation technique is very flexible, and this the primary reason behind its increase in the use of risk analysis. Most of the commonly used simulation techniques in assessing supply chain risk are multi-agent-based simulation (MAS) or agent-based simulation (ABS) (Mele et al., 2007; Giannakis and Louis, 2011; Cao and Chen, 2012), discrete-event simulation (DES) (Carvalho et al., 2012; Schmitt, 2009; Finke et al., 2010;), Monte Carlo simulation (Schmitt, 2009), Petri nets (Tuncel and Alpan, 2010) and system dynamics (SD) (Sidola et al., 2011).

Finally, Hybrid techniques are a mixture of both quantitative, qualitative, and methods. Hybrid technologies are efficient and useful for risk assessment where there is enormous uncertainty, and data relating risk is less available. Most frequently used hybrid techniques by the researcher in supply chain risk assessment are analytic hierarchy process (AHP) (Schoenherr et al., 2008; Sarrateet et al., 2005), fuzzy-AHP (Samvedi, Jain and Chan, 2013; Wang et al., 2012; Gupta, Sahu and Khandelwal., 2014; Mangla, Kumar and Barua, 2015), fuzzy-TOPSIS (Ganguly and Guin, 2011; Berenji and Anantharaman, 2011; Sun et al., 2015;), fuzzy interference system (FIS) (Behret, Başar, Öztayşi, and Kahraman, 2011) and fuzzy analytic network process (FANP)

(Moeinzadeh and Hajfathaliha, 2009; Berenji and Anantharaman, 2011) cluster analysis (Pavlou and Manthou, 2008) and decision tree analysis (DTA) (Jacinto and Silva, 2010).

In the current evolving era company's supply chains consist of a complex network of actors and activities prone to different risks linked to critical areas like upstream-downstream and operational. It's crucial for the organization and its supply chain manager to understand the supply chain system, supply chain partners, risk sources, and their consequences on the supply chain and organization. The companies should have to be proactive instead of reactive to manage their supply chains better. If the company is not dynamic in assessing and mitigating the risks in their supply chains, then the company's business is at risk (Mehmood et al., 2010). To protect the firm from losses, the firm needs to assess risks in its supply chains and make mitigation plans to control the situation before it gets worse. In today's challenging business environment, supply chain operations are disturbed by the different uncertainties prevailing inside and outside the business, like shortage of demand and supply, excess demand and supply, non-enforcement of law and order, political instability, resources unavailability, natural disaster, etc. These situations require organizations to make mitigation strategies and modify mitigation strategies according to the conditions (Rafique, 2015).

Undoubtedly, plenty of literature is available on supply chain risk and supply chain risk management in developed countries. Still, only a few studies are available when it comes to developing countries and especially Pakistan, which is not enough to write a literature review expressly limited to the country. The author found out only two studies relevant to the risk of a supply chain in Pakistan. A survey conducted by Mehmood et al., (2010), namely "managing supply chain risks in fresh food items," is associated with finding the riskiest factors in the supply chain of fresh eatables in Pakistan and presented the mitigation strategies for those risk. Moreover, Rafique (2015) conducted a study on "A fuzzy AHP-TOPSIS framework for the risk assessment of green supply chain implementation in the textile industry" and found some critical risk factors.

Automotive industry in Pakistan consist of small numbers of the manufacturer, vendors, and OEMs but still, it contributes to the economy in terms of revenue, foreign exchange, and employment. The automotive industry of Pakistan's annual turnover is calculated as PKR 30 billion. The sector consists of several producing units for original components and more than 2000 vendors with an investment of USD 1.09 billion. Regarding these statistics, as per the

author's information, no prior work is accessible that deals with supply chain risks of this specific sector in Pakistan. It would be the first attempt to explore this area and fulfill the research gap in the literature.

Analysis of Literature Review inside and Outside of Country

According to a study conducted on the Brazilian automotive industry, risks in the supply chain were categorized among four major categories according to their vulnerability or impact (i) Financial (ii) Strategic (iii) Hazard and (iv) Operational (Blos et al. 2009). Six risk factors, demand fluctuation risk, competitor's risk, purchase price risk, business process risk, alert mechanism risk, technical risks have a more considerable effect on the supply chains of automobile manufacturers in Guangxi, China (Feng et al. 2010). According to research on supply chain risk management in the German automotive industry, most automotive companies in Germany use preventive instruments to deal with risk rather than reactive devices. While it is also observed that large scale companies use precautionary tools while SMEs use responsive instruments more frequently (Thun and Hoenig, 2011b). Ceryno et al. (2014) classified supply chain risks into four categories (i) organizational risks, (ii) network related risks, (iii) industry-related risks, and (iv) environmental risks while assessing the risk in Brazilian automotive supply chains.

In research conducted on Supply chain risks among Malaysian automotive SMEs, three major risk types were analyzed in three different cases. These three risk types are:

- Internal to business,
- external to the company and internal to the distribution chain,
- external to supply chain, are the same explored by Christopher and Peck (2004) but with few modifications.

According to the study risks internal to the firm deals with Human related risks, while risks external to the firm internal to supply chain deals with different operational and process risks like quality problems, increased raw material price, supplier failure/bankruptcy, late deliveries, change in customers demand, global sourcing, and quality of raw material. Risks external to supply chain deals with those who are not in the control of organizations like Governmental regulations and forced events (Hudin et al. 2017).

A study carried out by Mehmood et al. (2010), namely "managing supply chain risks in fresh food items," is associated with discovering the riskiest factors in fresh food supply chains in

Pakistan and presented mitigation strategies for those risks. The research was conducted on the Makro Habib fresh food supply chain in Pakistan, and data was collected through interviews and questionnaires. According to the findings of the study, FIFO (loose practices), wrong ordering, and contamination of the product are the most critical risks in the supply chains of the fresh food industry. Moreover, Rafique (2015) conducted a study on "A fuzzy AHP-TOPSIS framework for the risk assessment of green supply chain implementation in the textile industry" and found some critical risk factors. Fuzzy multi-criteria group decision-making modeling (FMCGDM) is used for mitigating the consequences of the risk to evaluate the risks, which creates problems in implementing the green supply chain. The study used the fuzzy AHP and fuzzy TOPSIS technique to give weight and then rank the risk. The study's findings suggested some useful methods in mitigating risk during the implementation of the green supply chain. The latest research has been conducted by Junaid (2019) on "A Neutrosophic AHP and TOPSIS Framework for Supply Chain Risk Assessment in Automotive Industry of Pakistan." In his study, firstly, a structure for handling the uncertainties of the supply chain, is provided by its specific parameters, focused on the degree of proximity. Secondly, this work concerns first with the definition and evaluation of its most fragile threats in the automotive industry in Pakistan. Three risk assessment principles are defined and analyzed and can be used to establish risk reduction approaches. Finally, this analysis provides management with a clear description of the conditions in which the parameters are correctly applied. SCRs are assessed on a case-by-case basis, ranked in order of proximity, which indicates which risk can be better controlled by which criteria/procedures. Management teams in this sector should adopt the same method to establish prevention plans to mitigate and manage these risks.

Factor Analysis

Factorization/ Grouping, the risks of the supply chain into various factions, was achieved previously by many researchers, for instance, studies by Harland et al. (2003), Kleindorfer and Saad (2005), Gaonkar and Viswanadham (2007), Blos et al. (2009) Narasimhan and Talluri (2009), Tang and Nurmaya Musa (2011), Thun and Hoenig (2011), Shahbazi et al. (2013), Ceryno et al. (2015), Hudin and Hamid (2015), Levi et al. (2015), Sharma and Bhatt (2016), Mohamed and Youssef (2017) and Gautam et al. (2018). Supply chain risks can be classified into different categories and perspectives which deal with financial risk, corporate governance risk, procurement risk, supply risk, demand risk, and multi-level risk system on an aggregate basis. It

can be simplified into two main categories: internal and external (Christopher and Peck 2004). Due to globalization and turbulent changing environment in the world, manufacturers are forced to comply with the risk prevailing inside and outside their Supply chains. Incidents like 9/11, Hurricane Katrina, Tsunami, terrorist attacks, and catastrophes worldwide have uplifted the awareness of external supply chain risks. Apart from these external risks prevailing in the business world, there are multiple internal risks like quality problems, supply delays, IT failures, transportation failure, etc. disrupting the supply chains (Thun et al. 2011).

Christopher and Peck (2004) classified supply chain risk into three main categories (Internal to a firm, External to firm but internal to supply chain, External to supply chain and five (Process risk, control risk, demand risk, supply risk, and environmental risk) total categories under these three main categories. Chopra and Sodhi (2004) identified nine operational risk categories: procurement risk, disruptions, inventory risk, receivables, delays, system breakdowns, forecast error, and intellectual uncertainty. Factors such as outsourcing, lean production, reduced suppliers, and inventory reduction increase efficiency, but they are identified as the key supply chain risk drivers. In a study conducted on a famous automobile company, Volvo 16 different types of risk were analyzed. Internal risks were found severe and harmful for the supply chain, causing the most severe damage. Instead of just an equipment collapse, manufacturer loss, product quality issues, supply delays, increased consumer demand, transport loss, and malfunction of IT systems, they are found to have higher mean values and high risk. Moreover, natural disasters, oil crises, strikes, and terrorist attacks were the main external risk with lower mean values than internal risks (Shahbazi et al. 2013). Table 1 below presents different factors based on previous literature that affect the automotive industry's supply chains.

Table 1: Factor Analysis of Supply chain Risk

Factors/Sub factors	Description	References
Environmental Risks (ER)		
Natural disasters (ER11)	Risk arises due to events like earthquakes, fire, floods, hurricanes, etc.	Jüttner, Peck, and
Political unrest (ER1)	Risks associated with the political crisis that affects the businesses	Christopher (2003), Chopra

Economic instability (ER2)	Risks related to issues such as currency fluctuations, inflation, oil crises which cause supply disruptions	and Sodhi (2004),
Government restrictions (ER3)	Changing governmental Policies such as obstacles to immigration, limits on imports, raises in excise duty, and improvements in regulation raise risks to supply chains.	Christopher and Peck (2004), Zeng, Berger, and
Terrorist attacks (ER4)	Attacks like 9/11 which results in stopping the supply of Toyota resulting in loss of million dollars	Gerstenfeld (2005), Jüttner (2005), Wagner and Bode
Labor disputes (ER5)	The risk associated with labor such as strikes, payments, staff reduction, and downsizing and governmental wage rate change.	(2006), Wu, Blackhurst, and Vellayappan (2006), Rao and Goldsby (2009), Blos et al. (2009), Thun and Hoenig (2011), Sofyalıoğlu and Kartal (2012), Shahbazi et al. (2013), Ceryno et al. (2014),), Hudin and Hamid (2015), Levi et al. (2015), Sharma and Bhatt (2016),

		Mohamed and Youssef (2017) and Gautam et al. (2018)
Industry risks (IR)		
Input risk (IR1)	The risk associated with the acquisition of not lovely and good quality and quantity inputs during the production.	Zsidisin (2003), Rao and Goldsby (2009), Thun and Hoenig (2011), Chopra and Sodhi (2004), Jüttner (2005), Wagner and Bode (2006), Wu, Blackhurst, and Vellayappan (2006), Manuj and Mentzer (2008), Rao and Goldsby (2009), Thun and Hoenig (2011)
Product risk (IR2)	Risk arises due to change in customer taste, change in demand, availability of substitute goods, and scarce complementary products.	Chen and Paulraj (2004), Li and Lin (2006), Cucchiella and
Competitor risk (IR3)	The risk associated with the rival firm, its technology, products, human capital, and techniques.	

		Gastaldi (2006), Rao and Goldsby (2009), Blos et al. (2009)Shahbazi et al. (2013), Ceryno et al. (2014),), Hudin and Hamid (2015), Levi et al. (2015), Sharma and Bhatt (2016), Mohamed and Youssef (2017) and Gautam et al. (2018)
Organizational risks (OR)		
Liability risk (OR1)	Risk arises from the consumption or production of the product like product liability and emission of the pollutants.	Christopher and Peck (2004), Chopra and Sodhi (2004), Jüttner (2005), Zeng, Berger, and Gerstenfeld
Financial risk (OR2)	Risk arises due to the poor financial conditions, less cash at hand, collectible problems.	
Behavioral risk (OR3)	Risk arises due to the conflicts of managers and employees, corporate governance issues, and agency problems.	
R&D risk (OR4)	Risk arises due to issues in a new product, its design,	

	its features, etc.	(2005), Wagner and Bode
Technological risk (OR5)	Risk arises due to change in technology, misuse of technology, the use of outdated technology, or the use of labor, which is not skilled in using equipment or having a supplier with obsolete technology.	(2006), Bode (2006), Blackhurst, and
Communication risk (OR6)	Risk arises due to the failure of communication within and outside the organization. This communication can be company goals, strategies, and relationships.	Vellayappan (2006), Manuj and Mentzer (2008), Rao and Goldsby (2009),Blos et al. (2009), Thun and Hoenig (2011), Sofyalioğlu and Kartal (2012), Shahbazi et al. (2013), Ceryno et al. (2014), , Hudin and Hamid (2015), Levi et al. (2015), Sharma and Bhatt (2016), Mohamed and Youssef (2017) and Gautam et al. (2018)
Operational risks (OPR)		
Machine breakdown (OPR1)	The risk associated with machine breakdown, which can reduce production and increase the cost.	
Dysfunction of IT System (OPR2)	Risk arises due to the failure of the company IT system and a breakdown of communication within or outside the organization.	
Underutilized capacity (OPR3)	Risk arises from not using the organizational resources completely and not producing the goods to the highest capacity.	
Lead times (OPR4)	Risk arises due to taking more idle time and more spare time during the manufacturing process.	
Troubling third-party logistics (OPR5)	Not receiving material and raw goods on time can stop organizations' production, so having a logistic problem handler raises the risk.	
Human error (OPR6)	Errors caused by humans in the earlier stages of production can lead to more significant problems.	
Labor unrest (OPR7)	Labor strikes, labor sitting idle, and labor communication failure can raise the risk.	

Stream risks (SR)	Stream risk describes the flow of materials inside or outside; there are two streams of uncertainty; one is an upstream risk associated with the supply side. The other is a downstream risk associated with demand-side	
Upstream risk (UR)	Risks associated with the supply side in the supply chain	Jüttner (2005),
Supplier quality problem (UR1)	When the supplier provides low-quality products and then compromises over high-quality equipment risk arises in supply chains	Cucchiella and Gastaldi (2006), Wagner and Bode
Supplier delivery failure (UR2)	Risk arises due to product not delivered by the retailer on schedule, and it creates problems in production.	(2006), Manuj and Mentzer
Insolvency of the supplier (UR3)	Risk arises due to suppliers becomes insolvent and has insufficient funds to operate.	(2008), Blos et al. (2009),
Single-Sourcing (UR4)	Having a single supplier is a risk itself; if the supplier fails in delivering the product, the company faces enormous losses due to stopping production.	Thun and Hoenig (2011), Lavastre,
Increase in raw material prices (UR5)	The rise in the price of raw materials creates difficulties in procurement, and this kind of situation raises the risk for the supply chain.	Gunasekaran, and Spalanzani (2012),
Supplier communication failure (UR6)	When the distributor fails to disclose the production and delivery fault, the quality issues, or other difficulties on his side create damage to the organization.	Sofyalıoğlu and Kartal (2012), Shahbazi et al.

Upstream cargo damage (UR7)	Sometimes cargo damages create huge problems, operating on risky routes by logistics companies is a risk.	(2013), Ceryno et al. (2014),), Hudin and Hamid (2015), Levi et al. (2015), Sharma and Bhatt (2016), Mohamed and Youssef (2017) and Gautam et al. (2018)
Downstream risk (DR)	Risks connected with the demand side in the supply chain	
Demand fluctuations (DR1)	Change in demand due to seasonality, volatility, change in fashion and trends uplift the demand fluctuation risk	Jüttner (2005), Wagner and Bode (2006),
Inventory shortage (DR2)	Organizations try to cut inventory costs and use lean inventory techniques, which raises inventory shortage risk.	Manuj and Mentzer (2008), Thun
Delivery chain disruptions (DR3)	Delivery chain disruptions result in late deliveries to the customers, which creates an adverse impact and is a risk to company reputation.	and Hoenig (2011), Lavastre,
Forecasting error (DR4)	This risk arises while forecasting the demand for a product. Error in forecasting leads to organizational loss.	Gunasekaran, and Spalanzani (2012),
The decline in market prices (DR5)	A decline in market prices exposes supply chains to risk as the company will not be covering production costs.	Sofyalıoğlu and Kartal (2012),
Inflexibility (DR6)	Risk of losing market share in high demand due to	Shahbazi et al.

Bad customer relationship (DR7)	production inflexibility Bad customer relationship is a very vulnerable risk to the organization because spreading the lousy word of mouth can ruin the business.	(2013), Ceryno et al. (2014),), Hudin and Hamid (2015), Levi et al. (2015), Sharma and Bhatt (2016), Mohamed and Youssef (2017) and Gautam et al. (2018)
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Index System of Risk Assessment

After closed intact with the literature of supply chain risk generally and supply chain risk in the auto company specifically, we have proposed a risk assessment index system for the assessment of risk in supply chains of the vehicle sector in Pakistan. Supply chain risk factors in the automotive sector are divided into three major categories, five secondary categories and 34 risks in total, which are presented below in Table 2.

Table 2: Proposed supply chain risk assessment index system

Primary risk factors	Secondary risk factors	Details of index/risks
External	Environmental/Macro Economic	Natural disasters (ER11) Political unrest (ER1) Economic instability (ER2) Government restrictions (ER3) Terrorist attacks (ER4)
Internal	Industry risks (IR)	Input risk (IR1)

		Product risk (IR2)
		Competitor risk (IR3)
	Organizational risks (OR)	Liability risk (OR1)
		Financial risk (OR2)
		Behavioral risk (OR3)
		R&D risk (OR4)
		Technological risk (OR5)
		Communication risk (OR6)
	Operational risks (OPR)	Machine breakdown (OPR1)
		Malfunction of IT System (OPR2)
		Underutilized capacity (OPR3)
		Lead times (OPR4)
		Troubling third-party logistics (OPR5)
		Human error (OPR6)
		Labor unrest (OPR7)
Stream risks (SR)	Upstream risks (UR)	Supplier quality problem (UR1)
		Supplier delivery failure (UR2)
		Insolvency of the supplier (UR3)
		Single-Sourcing (UR4)
		Increase in prices of raw material (UR5)
		Supplier communication failure (UR6)
		Upstream cargo damage (UR7)
	Downstream risks (DR)	Demand fluctuations (DR1)

Inventory shortage (DR2)
Delivery chain disruptions
(DR3)
Forecasting error (DR4)
A decline in market prices
(DR5)
Inflexibility (DR6)
Bad customer relationship (DR7)

Conclusion

Contemporary SCRM literature also pays greater importance to the supply chain management of regular enterprises. The SCM feature and RM activities in flattened and versatile car firms have usually been overlooked. We found a missing connection between RM and SCM literature. We also noted that some of the supply chain procedures, such as risk evaluation in the business and handling such threats, are also being studied. In contrast, about criteria for managing those risks, very little or no research exists. This problem has indeed been introduced as highly significant in terms of recognizing the handling of supply chain threats in the automotive sector. While most SCRM research is undertaken from the perspective that which strategies should be used for managing these risks, we argue that research on SCRM in automobile companies must include:

- What is the most significant risk of a supply chain in the Pakistani automotive industry?
- What are some most relevant requirements/strategies for handling SCRs in the auto industry?
- What parameters are best performed in what conditions?

Limitations and Future Research Avenues

Due to differences like operations and businesses, we have focused only on the Pakistan automotive industry. The reason for choosing the automotive industry is that it is different from all other sectors and is much optimized and has multi-tier suppliers. It is a highly efficient, highly professional industry.

The research is only limited to the vehicle company in Pakistan and doesn't explore other sectors. The review results can vary from the analysis in the developed countries and the different industries due to the specific nature and behaviors of the automotive industry.

While this research adds a great deal to the studies on SCR management in various aspects, it is prone to limits that should be discussed in future researches. Firstly, this analysis deals with strategies for handling threats to the supply chain, but the dimensions and criteria have not been discussed. Therefore, a study that includes the requirements for managing SCRs in the automobile sector and the aspects of each risk and their capacity to control risks of supply chain and improve firm efficiency on a full scale is suggested. Secondly, this research deals only with the auto sector of Pakistan and, hence, its implementation to other fields is constrained. There is also a tremendous opportunity for analysis in the information technology, fabric, and electronics sectors to tackle the challenges in their production processes, as are developing economies in Pakistan and other emerging nations. Finally, this research describes the importance of just one state, and its validity to certain countries is restricted due to a variety of interpersonal and market eccentricities. In prospective analyses, for the future, a cross-country study is also suggested to generalize the findings.

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Conflicts of Interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

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